

RuleXploit: A Framework for Generating Suricata Rules from Exploits Using Generative AI

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Abstract—Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are essential for effective cyber-defense. Signature-based IDS operate using specific rules which are difficult to generate due to the evolving cybersecurity landscape. To this end, this work proposes a rule generation framework, called *RuleXploit*, which uses Large Language Models (LLMs) to generate rules from exploits. The proposed framework is composed of two components: the *RuleXploit Generator*, which produces rules using structured prompts and examples, and the *RuleXploit Refinery*, which validates and refines these rules for accuracy and effectiveness. The *RuleXploit* framework is demonstrated via the GPT-4o model, configured with tailored prompt engineering techniques and settings. *RuleXploit* successfully generated 100% syntactically valid rules and achieved an effectiveness rate of 76.67% in detecting malicious traffic. This work presents the first approach to generate IDS rules from the exploit code of a vulnerability, offering a novel way towards the successful mitigation of cyber attacks.

Index Terms—Intrusion Detection Systems, Cyber-attacks, Rule Generation, Vulnerabilities, Generative Artificial Intelligence, Large Language Models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are essential for detecting malicious activity and fall into two main categories: anomaly-based, which detects deviations from normal traffic, and signature-based, which relies on predefined rules to identify known threats [1]. Despite the significant advancements in anomaly-based IDS, particularly those based in Artificial Intelligence methods [2], signature-based IDS still remain widely used due to their reliability and precision [1].

Generating detection rules for IDS presents various challenges [3]. First, the overwhelming volume of new vulnerabilities and the escalating number of cyber-attacks make it difficult to keep rules updated [4]. Second, the process is highly resource-intensive, requiring significant time, effort, and expertise. Third, each IDS employs its own complex rule description language. Fourth, verifying the accuracy of these rules demands access to relevant data and a meticulous review process [3].

Various research efforts have focused on the automation of IDS rule generation using a range of approaches, such as Machine Learning (ML) [5], and, recently, Large Language Models (LLMs) [4]. These approaches typically utilize network traffic analysis, vulnerability descriptions or attack-specific datasets to generate rules. For instance, some studies generate IDS rules through SQL-like queries based on network

packet fields and protocols [6]. Others, automate the rule generation process by identifying common traffic patterns from network packet headers and payloads [7]. Specifically, ML models, such as Decision Trees (DTs), have been employed to generate rules for Suricata [5], a widely adopted IDS, specifically for DoS/DDoS attacks by training on legitimate and anomalous network traffic features [8]. Finally, LLMs have recently been explored for generating IDS rules by fine-tuning models with detailed attack-specific datasets [4].

Despite these advancements, existing efforts frequently depend on the quality of the datasets used for rule generation, involve complex workflows, require significant manual tuning, and cannot deal with the evolving cyber-attacks.

To address these shortcomings, this work introduces *RuleXploit*, a novel framework for IDS rule generation that consists of two key components: the *RuleXploit Generator*, which leverages an LLM to generate rules directly from exploits, and the *RuleXploit Refinery*, a quality assurance system, which validates the generated rules. The *RuleXploit Generator* utilizes a structured, prompt-based approach that incorporates detailed example rules, instructions, and an exploit of a vulnerability to produce a syntactically correct and precise rule, tailored to the provided exploit. Complementing the *RuleXploit Generator*, the *RuleXploit Refinery* evaluates the syntax and effectiveness of the generated rule in terms of both syntax validity and its ability to detect the cyber-attacks associated with the exploit. If a rule is found to be syntactically invalid or ineffective, the *RuleXploit Generator* is rerun to produce a new rule tailored to the corresponding exploit. The newly generated rule is then evaluated by the *RuleXploit Refinery*, and this iterative process continues until a rule that is both syntax valid and effective is generated. The *RuleXploit* framework is demonstrated through the utilization of OpenAI’s GPT-4o model [9], [10], specific prompt engineering instructions, and GPT-4o’s configurations to generate Suricata rules. GPT-4o was chosen as it is one of the most widely used LLMs [11]. Similarly, Suricata was selected for the demonstration due to its wide adoption [5].

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time IDS rules have been automatically generated directly from exploits utilizing LLMs. While the *RuleXploit* framework automates rule generation and validation, minimal human intervention may be required for instruction refinement in edge cases.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Proposal of a framework capable of using LLMs to generate IDS rules directly from the exploit part of a vulnerability, as well as refining and validating the generated rules.
- Demonstration of the proposed framework using the GPT-4o model to generate Suricata IDS rules.
- Evaluation of the proposed framework for a selection of exploits achieving 100% syntactically valid rules and an effectiveness rate of 76.67% in detecting malicious traffic.
- Addressing limitations of existing rule generation methods, such as reliance on high-quality datasets, complex manual workflows and tuning, and inability to adapt to the evolving cyber-attacks.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section II provides the background for the rest of the paper. Section III presents work related to IDS rule generation. Section IV details the proposed framework. Section V describes an implementation instance of the proposed framework and Section VI presents the experimental results on this implementation instance. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. BACKGROUND

This section provides an overview of the foundational concepts of the paper.

A. Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures

The Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs) is a catalog of known vulnerabilities of platforms (i.e., software and hardware) [12]. Each CVE contains various properties, including a unique identifier (CVE ID), such as "CVE-2023-28432" and a description of the vulnerability written in a human-readable format. For example, the description of "CVE-2023-28432" [13], which is provided below, outlines a security vulnerability in MinIO.

MinIO is a Multi-Cloud Object Storage framework. In a cluster deployment starting with RELEASE.2019-12-17T23-16-33Z and prior to RELEASE.2023-03-20T20-16-18Z, MinIO returns all environment variables, including MINIO_SECRET_KEY and MINIO_ROOT_PASSWORD, resulting in information disclosure. All users of distributed deployment are impacted. All users are advised to upgrade to RELEASE.2023-03-20T20-16-18Z.

B. Exploit

An exploit corresponds to a code that leverages a CVE to compromise a vulnerable platform. Exploits can be found across various sources, such as the Exploit Database (Exploit-DB) [14], and GitHub or community-contributed repositories, such as [15]. For example, the exploit [16] (see below) of the aforementioned "CVE-2023-28432" vulnerability uses an HTTP POST request to target the endpoint "/minio/bootstrap/v1/verify" of a MinIO instance to expose sensitive environment variables, including credentials.

```
POST /minio/bootstrap/v1/verify HTTP/1.1 Host:
your-ip:9000 User-Agent: Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT
10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML,
like Gecko) Chrome/110.0.5481.178 Safari/537.36
Connection: close Cache-Control: max-age=0
Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded
```

C. Suricata

Suricata is an open-source network intrusion detection and prevention system (IDS/IPS) [17]. Suricata is used to identify specific traffic by analyzing exchanged network traffic packets and matching them against predefined rules. Suricata ensures two critical metrics for any rule:

- **Syntax Correctness:** Suricata validates the structure and syntax of each rule before use. Rules must adhere to Suricata's structured format to ensure they are properly parsed. If a rule contains syntax errors, Suricata will reject it and log the error, preventing its utilization.
- **Detection Effectiveness:** A rule is effective, if it successfully generates an alert for the traffic described in the rule. Effectiveness is evaluated during live traffic inspection by testing whether the rule triggers an alert for the desired traffic or not. Even a syntactically correct rule can fail to be effective, if its criteria do not align precisely with the traffic pattern it intends to detect.

Each Suricata rule follows a structured syntax, consisting of two main components: a header and a set of options;

- **Header:** Specifies the fundamental traffic properties that define basic criteria for detecting traffic. Some examples include the communication protocol (e.g., HTTP or FTP), source and destination IP addresses, and port numbers.
- **Options:** Provide more detailed criteria to match patterns within the traffic, such as HTTP methods, URI paths, or payloads. Further options include references (e.g., CVE identifiers), and metadata (e.g., rule identifiers) about the traffic.

For example, the Suricata rule listed below detects traffic related to the exploitation of the "CVE-2023-28432". The header of the rule specifies that traffic uses the HTTP protocol, originates from any source, and targets any destination (i.e., http any any → any any). The options part specifies that the traffic targets the URI path "/minio/bootstrap/v1/verify" (http.uri; content: "/minio/bootstrap/v1/verify";) via the POST method (http.method; content: "POST") and that the session terminates after the request (flow: to_server;). The options part also includes the Suricata "fast_pattern" command to optimize detection, a reference to "CVE-2023-28432" (reference:cve,2023-28432;), the unique identifier of the rule (sid:2047923;), and the rule revision number (rev:1;).

```
alert http any any → any any (msg:"ET
WEB_SPECIFIC_APPS MinIO Information
Disclosure Attempt (CVE-2023-28432)";
flow: to_server; http.method; content:"POST";
http.uri; content: "/minio/bootstrap/v1/verify";
sid:2047923; rev:1;
```

D. Generative Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has garnered significant attention, due to the emergence of Generative AI and, more specifically, of LLMs. These models, trained on vast amounts of data, have demonstrated remarkable capabilities across various tasks [18]. A key feature of LLMs is their capacity for in-context learning, where they generate text based on specific contexts (prompts) [19], enhancing their relevance and coherence in interactive uses.

As LLMs are though prone to creating erroneous or fictional information [18], various techniques and metrics have been proposed to mitigate these issues. The most notable such technique, and also a very important research topic, is prompt engineering, which involves crafting inputs to guide the model in producing accurate and relevant outputs. This process includes several key aspects, such as the concept of "shot inference", which specifies the content that is given to an LLM before answering a given question. For example, in zero-shot inference, no prior examples related to the task are given to the model, relying entirely on its training to generate a response. Conversely, few-shot inference involves providing a limited number of task-related examples to guide the model's response. This guidance can significantly improve the precision and relevance of the responses [20].

Another important aspect of prompt engineering is the framing of questions and instructions in the right format. Many LLMs, like GPT-4o, utilize both a "user prompt" and a "system prompt" to guide the response of a model. The system prompt establishes the model's behavior by providing it with a specific role, tone, style, specific instructions, and any constraints it should follow, while the user prompt specifies the context and the exact task or query. Together, they enable the model to produce responses that align with the LLM-defined role and instructions, while remaining tailored to the given task.

Temperature is a critical parameter that plays a significant role in addressing the tendency of LLMs to produce erroneous or fictional information. Temperature determines the randomness or creativity of LLM outputs by using the model's probability distribution during text generation [21]. A lower temperature value can make the model too specific and, in turn, prevent it from providing more contextual rich answers. Conversely, a higher temperature value can make the model more random, which may lead to answers that are far from anticipated. The temperature value can vary.

III. RELATED WORK

Various research efforts have addressed IDS rule generation through a wide range of techniques, from manual approaches to semi-automated and fully automated techniques.

For example, the researchers in [6] developed a platform to simplify the creation of IDS rules through a user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI), designed for non-experienced users. Rules were defined as SQL-like queries and were created, managed, and applied in real-time through the GUI. More specifically, the rule creation process utilized packet fields and

protocol indicators, like ICMP type or code, to define SQL-like queries that directly mapped to these characteristics.

In [8], the researchers proposed an automated Suricata rule generation method using ML methods for identifying DoS/DDoS attacks. They used DTs trained on legitimate and anomalous network traffic, selecting features that map to Suricata syntax. The DT's decision rules were derived from traffic features and were converted into Suricata rules with predefined structures. The process ensured that each rule captures key traffic characteristics associated with anomalous behavior, like payload size or TCP flags. Compared to manual methods and existing tools, their method offered a faster execution and reduced rule complexity, making it an efficient solution for automating IDS rule creation.

In [22], the authors proposed an automated procedure for generating rules using ML techniques for another popular IDS called Snort. The CICFlowMeter tool was used to extract over 80 statistical features from network traffic data, such as packet size and duration, which were input into a DT algorithm. The DT was chosen for its ability to produce interpretable decision criteria, such as conditions on packet size or destination port, which are directly translatable into Snort rule syntax. A Python script was used to automate the conversion and integration of these rules into the Snort IDS ruleset, providing real-time detection of both known and emerging network attacks.

One more automated ML-based IDS rule procedure was presented in [23]. Initially, network traffic features were extracted and provided as input to various ML models like Logistic Regression, CART, Naive Bayes, AdaBoost, and Random Forest classifier (RFC). The RFC model was chosen due to its superior performance and was transformed into a set of rules compatible with IDS tools like Snort and Suricata. In particular, DT paths from root to leaf nodes were transformed into conditional rules in an "if-then" format, capturing attack patterns such as flow rates, packet directions, and port activities. The system achieved high effectiveness, with some attack types reaching 100% precision and a detection rate over 99%.

In [4], different LLMs, namely ChatGPT 3.5, LLaMA 2 7B, Mistral 7B, GPT4, Falcon, Nous-Hermes, and Wizard v1.1, as well as LLM fine-tuning approaches were used to generate rules for firewalls and IDS. A custom dataset was created, mapping attack scenarios (e.g., DoS, buffer overflows, SQL injections) to iptables and Snort rules. Rules were generated using detailed attack-specific attributes, such as malformed packets, protocol misuse, and flow behaviors. Mistral 7B performed best after fine-tuning, achieving 89% accuracy. The researchers' findings suggest that while fine-tuning can enhance the accuracy of chatbot-generated rules, human oversight is crucial before applying these outputs in practical security settings.

Contrary to existing research, this study focuses on generating IDS rules from the exploit of vulnerabilities. Unlike existing work that relies on vulnerability descriptions, general datasets, or predefined traffic patterns, the proposed RuleXploit framework analyzes the exploit and follows detailed instructions to generate IDS rules. This method provides a more

actionable approach for rule generation, as it captures the actual techniques and payloads used in real-world attacks, in turn, enhancing the detection accuracy.

IV. RULEXPLOIT FRAMEWORK

RuleXploit is a framework designed to generate IDS rules from exploits using Generative AI. As illustrated in Figure 1, RuleXploit consists of two components: the RuleXploit Generator and the RuleXploit Refinery. The RuleXploit Generator is actually an LLM that focuses on generating rules based on the LLM’s configurations, exploits, structured examples, CVE descriptions, and a set of instructions that guide the LLM’s behavior (i.e., prompt engineering). The generated rules are then passed to the RuleXploit Refinery to validate their syntactic correctness and detection effectiveness. The RuleXploit Refinery operates in a controlled virtualized environment, simulating exploit-based traffic to evaluate whether the generated rule is syntax-valid and detection effective. If the rule fails one of these checks, the RuleXploit Generator iteratively creates a new rule, repeating the process until a syntax-valid and detection effective rule is generated. This iterative cycle ensures the production of high-quality, deployable IDS rules.

A. RuleXploit Generator

The RuleXploit Generator is responsible for generating IDS rules tailored to a specific exploit via an LLM. The RuleXploit Generator operates by integrating three core LLM components, the User Prompt and System Prompt components that provide specific content and guidance to the model, and the LLM’s configurations that define the operational LLM’s behavior.

- **User Prompt Component:** This serves as the primary input to the LLM that provides the necessary data, and context for rule generation. It entails the following:
 - **Structured examples.** These serve as a learning foundation for the LLM by providing context for the task. Each example consists of a CVE description, exploit code, and a valid and effective rule. For instance, an example may include a CVE description of a vulnerability in an HTTP service, the exploit code targeting that vulnerability, and an effective IDS rule to detect traffic associated with the exploit.
 - **Exploit.** This corresponds to the exploit from which the IDS rule will be generated. An exploit can be in text, script, or programming language form and is processed by the RuleXploit Generator to extract the necessary technical details for rule generation.
 - **CVE Description.** This corresponds to the description of the CVE associated with the above exploit. This description helps the LLM to enhance the rule with metadata, such as alert messages and references.
 - **Task Definition.** This corresponds to the task that is assigned to the LLM. For example, the task could be phrased as: "Generate a Suricata rule for the provided CVE based on its exploit code".
- **System Prompt Component:** This serves as a guide for shaping the LLM’s behavior during rule generation. It

consists of a **Set of Instructions** that directs the LLM to generate IDS rules that are both syntactically valid and practically effective at detecting exploit-associated traffic. These instructions do not have to be generated all at once, but can be iteratively refined through experimentation. By debugging multiple exploit scenarios via the feedback of the RuleXploit Refinery, the users of RuleXploit may identify errors in syntax and ineffectiveness in detecting exploit-associated traffic; these observations have the potential to enable users to iteratively refine and update the instructions.

It should be noted that both the system and user prompts were considered for placing the Set of Instructions. While including all instructions within the user prompt was a viable alternative, it was observed that the placement of the instructions within the system prompt demonstrated better results in terms of valid and effective rules.

The instructions of this set are grouped into the following four categories:

- 1) **Syntax Corrections Instruction Group:** This group addresses syntax issues that can render rules invalid or unusable by the IDS. Issues like incorrect handling of escape sequences, special characters, non-English text, numbers, and symbols, might be frequently encountered. Such issues cause rules to fail validation and be ignored by the IDS. Consequently, these instructions should ensure that rules comply with IDS’s strict syntax requirements and avoid common errors that can render rules unusable.
- 2) **Rule Effectiveness Instruction Group:** This group ensures that the generated rules effectively detect traffic and accurately map the exploit elements to the appropriate rule fields. Some rules might fail to trigger alerts (i.e., detect the desired traffic) due to incorrect mapping or the omission of critical rule components.
- 3) **Testing and Validation Instruction Group:** This group aims to simplify the testing and validation of the generated rules via the RuleXploit Refinery, while ensuring their broad applicability in diverse network environments, such as Virtual LANs and external public networks. Some rules might exclude local IP addresses, causing the IDS to overlook traffic originating from or destined to local IP addresses. Since the RuleXploit Refinery’s testing environment relies on local traffic to evaluate rule syntax and effectiveness, it is crucial to ensure all local traffic is captured during its validation process.
- 4) **LLM Behavior Guidance Instruction Group:** This group ensures that the LLM generates rules strictly based on the exploit, without adding any extra content or misbehaving. Based on the nature of LLMs, some rules might include details not present in the exploit, leading to rules that are inaccurate or unrelated to the specific exploit.

Fig. 1. RuleXploit Framework

- **Configurations.** These are the operational settings of LLMs, such as the temperature value that influences the model’s behavior during rule generation. Each setting should be carefully selected to achieve an optimal balance between predictability and creativity. For instance, Section VI sets the temperature value to 0.6 to strike this balance effectively.

B. RuleXploit Refinery

The RuleXploit Refinery serves as the validation component of the proposed framework, ensuring that the generated rules meet both the syntactic and effectiveness requirements. To do so, the RuleXploit Refinery evaluates the rules generated by the RuleXploit Generator and determines their quality based on two key criteria: syntax validity and detection effectiveness.

The RuleXploit Refinery is actually a Virtual Machine (VM) running an operating system like Linux. As depicted in Figure 1, an IDS is deployed within the RuleXploit Refinery VM. Additionally, another VM, referred to as Vulnerable VM, is installed inside the RuleXploit Refinery VM to host a platform vulnerable to a desired exploit. This setup allows for a realistic simulation of cyber-attacks, while isolating and protecting the systems outside the RuleXploit Refinery. To simulate a cyber-attack, the user executes the exploit against the vulnerable VM using either a terminal or automated tools designed for testing security vulnerabilities. After the exploit is executed, the generated rule is integrated into the IDS, where it is evaluated for two critical aspects: syntax validity and effectiveness in detecting the malicious traffic associated with the exploit.

The main steps in the RuleXploit Refinery workflow are:

- 1) **Syntax Validation:** Each generated rule is tested for compatibility with the syntax of the IDS. For this purpose, the generated rules are added to the IDS, and if they fail in syntax, they are flagged as invalid.
- 2) **Traffic Simulation:** Network traffic is simulated by executing the exploit against the vulnerable VM. This

process replicates the malicious activity associated with the exploit, generating the traffic that will be analyzed.

- 3) **Detection Testing:** The IDS instance processes the simulated traffic using the generated rule. The rule’s effectiveness is determined based on its ability to accurately detect and trigger alerts for the cyber-attack of the exploit that tries to leverage a vulnerability.
- 4) **Feedback Mechanism:** If a rule passes both syntax validation and detection testing, it is marked as ready for deployment in the IDS. However, if the rule fails either test, feedback is sent back to the RuleXploit Generator. The user analyzes the identified issues, such as syntax errors or detection failures, and decides whether to rerun the RuleXploit Generator or refine the “Set of Instructions” in the System Prompt to address the problem. Given the stochastic nature of LLMs, the RuleXploit Generator may need to run multiple runs to address variability before updating the “Set of Instructions”. This loop continues until the Refinery validates a rule as both syntactically correct and effective.

V. RULEXPLOIT FRAMEWORK DEMONSTRATION

This section demonstrates the RuleXploit framework using the GPT-4o model to generate Suricata IDS rules.

A. RuleXploit Generator Implementation

This section describes the specific implementation of the components of the RuleXploit Generator evaluation in this work, namely specific implementation of the User and System Prompt components, along with the LLM’s configurations.

The **User Prompt** consists of the following inputs:

- **Structured examples:** Each such example comprises a CVE description, the corresponding exploit code, and the relevant Suricata rule. CVE data is sourced from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) of NIST [12], while exploit codes are obtained from an open-source repository of pre-built vulnerable virtual machines [15].

- **Exploit:** This corresponds to the exploit from which the Suricata rule is generated. The exploit code was sourced from an open-source repository of pre-built vulnerable virtual machines [15].
- **CVE Description:** This corresponds to the description of the CVE that is associated with the above exploit.
- **Task Definition:** The task presented to the LLM is stated verbatim as follows: *"Generate a Suricata rule for the provided CVE based on its exploit code. Use the examples for guidance and follow the instructions below"*. The aforementioned task definition was derived after taking into account specific considerations; more specifically, by specifying both the desired format (*Suricata rule*) and the input context (*provided CVE and exploit code*), we tried to minimize the ambiguity and ensure that the LLM understands the expected output. Our end goal was to make the model stay focused on the task and in turn augment the precision and clarity of the task. In addition, by guiding the model to take the examples into account (*use the examples for guidance*), we offered to the model concrete references for the anticipated rule structure and syntax and therefore improved the consistency and accuracy of the generated rules. Last, the incorporation of specific instructions (*follow the instructions below*) helped the model to generate correct and effective rules free of errors and inconsistencies.

The **System Prompt** consists of the following:

- 1) **Syntax Corrections Instruction Group:** During the development of the RuleXploit Generator, it became evident that exploits containing backslashes, non-English characters, numbers, and symbols often resulted in errors in various rule fields. These errors rendered the rules syntactically invalid and unusable in Suricata. To overcome these challenges, a set of targeted instructions was introduced to guide GPT-4o in generating rules that adhered to Suricata's syntax requirements. The final set of instructions used for prompting the LLM for this group is stated verbatim as follows:

- **Escaping Single Backslashes:** *"In Suricata rules, when you are going to use the content field within http.request_body because of the exploit, if the value of the exploit contains a single backslash (\), it must be escaped with a backslash (\\) first and then populate the http.request_body content"*.
- **Escaping Double Backslashes:** *"If the exploit contains double backslashes (e.g., \\ or \\\), each must be escaped as well"*.
- **Validate Escapes in Exploits:** *"Ensure that you read the exploit correctly and validate the number of backslashes in any escape sequences within the generated rule"*.
- **No Escape Characters in Exploits:** *"Important note: The exploit does not contain any escape characters (e.g., a single backslash) in its literal*

form".

- **Handling Non-English Characters:** *"When the body of the exploit contains non-English characters, numbers, or symbols (e.g., %7B, %22, {}, []), you must ignore these characters and you must use only the text in plain English letters (A-Z, a-z) that exists between these characters to generate the http.request_body content field"*. For this instruction, the decision to focus on plain English text stems from Suricata's inability to automatically decode symbols or encoded characters like %7B, which can result in syntactic errors if included directly. This decision simplifies the rule generation process for the LLM and ensures the generated rules are syntactically valid and effective. While some encoded characters may carry meaning, this trade-off prioritizes reliability and generalizability of the rules across diverse scenarios.

- 2) **Rule Effectiveness Instruction Group:** The RuleXploit Refinery helped to identify that some rules failed to trigger alerts (i.e., detect the desired traffic) due to incorrect mapping of exploit elements to appropriate rule fields or the omission of critical rule components. To address these issues, a set of precise and targeted instructions was formulated to ensure that the content of the exploit is correctly assigned to relevant fields in the rule and that the rules are robust in identifying associated traffic patterns. For instance, the instructions emphasize the proper use of sticky buffers, accurate processing of HTTP bodies, and correct classification of connection states. The instructions used for prompting the LLM to address these challenges are:

- **Use of Sticky Buffer:** *"You must always use the http.uri.raw sticky buffer in the Suricata rule and not the http.uri sticky buffer"*.
- **Mapping Exploit Components to Rule Fields:** *"Be sure that the contents of the URL of the exploit is used in the http.uri.raw fields, the headers of the exploit in the http.header_names fields, and the content of the body of the exploit in the http.request_body fields"*.
- **URL Strings in the Correct Field:** *"Strings in the URL of the exploit must be in the http.uri.raw; content and not in the http.request_body; content"*.
- **Non-Empty http.request_body:** *"If you use the http.request_body with the content field, be sure that the content is not empty. For example this is not valid http.request_body; content: ""; because the content is empty. If the exploit does not use http body do not include the http.request_body; content: ""; in the rule"*.
- **Connection State Check:** *"Check the exploit for the connection state (e.g., close) and*

use the appropriate Flow Keyword, such as `flow:established,to_server;`, when the connection is established or `flow:to_server;` when the connection is not established”.

- **Avoid pcre Field:** “You must never use `pcre` in Suricata rules”.

3) **Testing and Validation Instruction Group:** The RuleXploit Refinery helped to observe that some rules excluded local IP addresses, causing Suricata to overlook traffic originating from or destined to local IP addresses. Given that the RuleXploit Refinery’s testing environment relied on local traffic to evaluate rule syntax and effectiveness, we need to ensure that all local traffic was captured during evaluation. For this, the instruction below was used for prompting the LLM and ensure that the generated rules can apply to traffic from any IP and port to any IP and port, while maintaining the specific protocol used in the exploit.

- **Starting Rule Format:** “Always start your rule with the following format: `alert [protocol] any any -> any any (msg: "..."). Replace [protocol] with the appropriate protocol, such as HTTP or TCP”`

4) **LLM Behavior Guidance Instruction Group** To ensure that GPT-4o generates rules strictly based on the exploit, without adding any extra content, the instruction presented below was used for prompting the LLM.

- **Match Only Actual Content:** “Ensure the content you are matching is actually present in the exploit. Do not create or fabricate any information”.

Configurations. GPT-4o was set to operate with a temperature value of 0.6 as it became evident that other settings near to the mean of the temperature values supported by the model (0–2) [24] (e.g., 1.2) included extra content beyond the exploit code in the rules. In particular, values close to 2 make the generated rules more generic and insert new unrelated information.

B. RuleXploit Refinery Implementation

The RuleXploit Refinery was implemented using an Ubuntu Linux 22.04 VM. Within this VM, vulnerable VMs were deployed from [15], simulating targets for the exploits. The Ubuntu terminal was used to execute the exploits from [15] against these vulnerable VMs.

For simplicity, the implementation example focused on exploits written in text-based formats that use web communication protocols, such as HTTP, HTTPS, or FTP. These formats were selected because they can be executed effectively using cURL (client URL) [25] making it an ideal choice for executing compatible exploits in a simple way.

The Suricata version 7.0.6 was installed on the Ubuntu VM to monitor and analyze traffic between the terminal and the vulnerable VMs. Suricata played a critical role in validating the syntax and effectiveness of the generated rules.

VI. EVALUATION RESULTS

This section presents the results of running the implemented instance presented in Section V. The development phase of this instance was completed after seven iterations on two exploits for the vulnerabilities of CVE-2024-15077 and CVE-2021-25646 obtained from [15]. These iterations were used for refining the prompt engineering strategy and configurations. Once the refinements were completed, the implemented instance of the proposed framework was considered stable and ready for evaluation.

For the evaluation, a set of 10 exploits obtained from [15] were used as input to the implemented instance and IDS rules were generated without any additional iterations and refinements. While the sample size of 10 may appear limited, it was chosen so as to focus on exploits executable via cURL. The selection was also guided by the availability of pre-configured vulnerable VMs, avoiding the need for custom infrastructure and potential biases from manual setup. To account for the stochastic nature of LLMs, each rule was generated across three independent runs of the RuleXploit Generator.

The results of the evaluation are presented below:

- **Successful Cases:** Five CVEs, namely, CVEs 2023-42793, 2023-28432, 2022-46169, 2020-13942, and 2019-10758, achieved consistent success across all three runs, passing both syntactic validation and effectiveness testing. For these rules, the RuleXploit Refinery did not trigger any feedback.
 - **Partially Successful Cases:**
 - CVE 2023-32315 and CVE-2019-15107 failed to trigger alerts in one of the three runs. This issue was due to minor inconsistencies in how specific exploit components were mapped to Suricata rule fields as spotted by the RuleXploit Refinery.
 - CVEs 2021-25646 and 2021-3129 exhibited failures in effectiveness during the first run. The RuleXploit Refinery spotted misaligned criteria in rules (e.g., content or flow-related fields).
 - **Challenging Case:** CVE 2020-7961 was particularly difficult. Although all generated rules were syntactically valid, none could effectively detect traffic. This failure stemmed from the exploit’s complexity, where critical exploit parts (e.g., payloads) were not accurately captured by the RuleXploit Generator to be included in the rule. This highlights the need for further instruction refinement or additional iterations for complex exploits.
- Overall, the RuleXploit framework demonstrated significant potential in automating IDS rule generation, as shown in Table I, by achieving:
- **High Validity Rate:** RuleXploit successfully generated 100% syntactically valid rules across all tested exploits and runs.
 - **Strong Detection Performance:** 76.67% of the generated rules effectively detected the traffic across all three runs.

TABLE I
EVALUATION RESULTS.

V = VALID (I.E., SYNTACTICALLY CORRECT), VE = VALID & EFFECTIVE (I.E., TRIGGERED AN ALERT). GREEN: FULLY SUCCESSFUL, ORANGE: PARTIALLY SUCCESSFUL, RED: CHALLENGING CASE.

CVE	Runs						Total	
	1		2		3		# Runs	
	V	VE	V	VE	V	VE	V	VE
2023-42793	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	3
2023-32315	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	3	2
2023-28432	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	3
2022-46169	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	3
2021-25646	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	2
2021-3129	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	2
2020-13942	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	3
2020-7961	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	3	0
2019-15107	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	3	2
2019-10758	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	3
Total	100%	70%	100%	80%	100%	80%	100%	76.67%

- **Complex Exploits:** One particularly complex exploit remained undetected, which underscores the need for future enhancements in prompt engineering and instruction refinement.

VII. CONCLUSION

This work introduced the novel RuleXploit framework for generating IDS rules directly from exploits using an LLM. The proposed framework addresses critical challenges in IDS rule generation, such as the time-intensive nature of manual processes, the need for domain expertise, and the dynamic nature of cyber-attacks. The framework consists of two main components: the RuleXploit Generator, which produces IDS rules through structured user and system prompts, and the RuleXploit Refinery, which validates the generated rules for syntax and effectiveness. The iterative feedback mechanism between these components ensures the generation of high-quality rules. Experimental results via GPT-4o demonstrated the framework’s capability to consistently generate syntactically valid and effective rules for the Suricata IDS. However, they also highlighted cases for improvements, indicating the complexity of translating exploit elements into accurate detection rules. Future enhancements could focus on broadening exploit coverage, optimizing prompts, and designing novel architectures using LLM agents for improved performance. In addition, the generation processes for rules based on network traffic logs will be explored using Retrieval-Augmented Generation architectures and Knowledge Graphs.

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